

Supervision Panacea for Delivery of Quality Education in Correctional Centre in Nigeria

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Abstract: *This paper discussed the benefits of correctional education supervision in Nigeria. The paper used secondary data. The secondary data were collected from online publications and print resources. Content analysis was used to select the final literatures for the paper. The paper concluded that supervision of correctional education in Nigeria will lead to improvement in facilitators' job performance, attainment of correctional education goals, improvement in inmate academic performance and improvement in the quality of teaching-learning in the correctional education in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the paper recommends that the government through the agencies in charge of instructional supervision to improve the quality of instructional supervision in all the correctional centres. Government should adequately fund these agencies to enable them carry out their supervisory functions.*

Keywords: *Correctional education, Supervision, Schools.*

1.0 Introduction

Correctional or prison education is *any educational activity that occurs inside prison*. Courses can include basic literacy programmes, secondary school equivalency. Prison education, also known as Inmate Education and Correctional Education, is an expansive term encompassing any educational activities occurring inside a prison. These educational activities include both vocational training and academic education. The goal of such activities is to prepare the prisoner for success outside of prison and to enhance the rehabilitative aspects of prison. Educational programs offered inside prisons are typically provided and managed by the prison systems in which they reside. Funding for the programs is provided through official correctional department budgets, private organizations (e.g., colleges, nonprofits, etc.), and the prisoners or their families if the prisoner is pursuing education through a correspondence program (Zoukis, 2011).

Education in Nigerian prisons is a tool for the restoration of these persons to the path of rectitude. Vocational education would enable them to acquire skills they can live on after their discharge from prison. NPS adopted the Adult and Remedial Education Programme (AREP) as a means of educating inmates, allowing them to reconnect with their educational needs and aspirations (Ogundipe, 2008). Prison education is the form of education designed for prisoners to enable them leave the prison with more skills and be in a position to find meaningful employment or create employment. In agreement

with the above definitions, prison education is education designed for prisoners to equip them with veritable skills and knowledge to enable them to be productive on release (Rhode 2004). Prison education is an organized educational activity that occurs inside prison with the aims of modifying the prisoner's orientation. Prison education is an education meant to reform the prisoner and make them useful to the society. Programme in prison education include basic literacy programs, secondary school equivalency programs, vocational education, and tertiary education (Ogunode Edinoh, & Odo, 2023).

Prison education is a broad term that encompasses number of educational activities, occurring inside a prison. These educational activities include both vocational training, academic and general education. The goal of such activities is to prepare a prisoner for successful adjustment outside the prison. Education programmes that take place inside prisons are completely provided and managed by the prison authorities (Wikipedia, 2014). Wolford (1989) notes that the purpose of prison or correctional education can be classified into six key factors: To provide inmates with basic academic and vocational skills; to provide inmates with an opportunity to change their personal behaviours and values; to reduce recidivism; to provide passive control of inmates' behaviour to support the operational needs of the correctional institution and to provide institutional work assignments. . From the above, correctional education is the education that takes place in the prison yard with the aims of empowering the inmates with relevant skills and knowledge that will be them useful after their jail time. Correctional education is the teaching and learning that is done in the prison with the goals of equipping inmates with vocational and academic skills. Educational opportunities can be divided into two general categories: academic education and vocational training.

Academic education is usually provided through GED or literacy classes (Gerald, 2008). These free classes assist the prisoner in learning to read, write, and perform basic mathematical computations. This is especially important in a correctional setting because, compared to the general population, prisoners are an under-educated group – who maintain less than 5th-grade proficiency in reading and writing (Brazzell, Lindahl, & Solomon, (2009) – coming from a culture of poverty, with few skills for handling everyday tasks, and little or no experience in a trade or career (Zoukis, 2011). Hence, many require significant remedial help before attending more advanced educational classes (Gerald, 2008). These classes aim to prepare the prisoner to take the official GED tests – the official high school diploma equivalent – and to hopefully further their education with more advanced studies. Other free basic forms of academic education, which are on the level of the GED courses or below, include English-as-a-Second Language classes and special education classes. One, none, or both will be offered depending on the facility.

Past this basic level of academic education is a college education. While the most effective way to offer advanced college-level programs in prisons is to partner with local colleges and universities willing to send in teachers (Erisman & Contardo, 2005), this rarely happens because of funding and staffing concerns. Hence, in terms of advanced academic education, the prisoners' best bet is to enroll in college correspondence courses. These courses from legitimate colleges are delivered in a correspondence format. These courses are not free to the prisoner. The prisoner must find a way to pay for the courses up-front (e.g., through their own means, family members, or other organizations). College correspondence courses usually cost several hundred dollars apiece (Zoukis, 2011).

Vocational training, on the other hand, offers more opportunities in the prison setting. Much of what is provided will depend upon the local prison's programming. At FCI-Petersburg, we can learn Computer-Aided Design, Carpentry, and several other vocations via "live-work" employment (e.g., plumbing, electricity, landscaping). All of these are free to the prisoner participants. The prisoner can usually enroll in vocational correspondence education outside the prison setting. These include legal studies, mediation, religious studies, and much more. All costs and fees are the responsibility of the individual prisoner and usually run from several hundred dollars per course to several thousand per program of

study. Vocational training via correspondence is almost exclusively less expensive than correspondence academic education (Zoukis, 2011).

Ogbaka et al., (2017) summarily posited that there are three main objectives of prison education at the primary level, which cut across different views of the purpose of the criminal justice system. These include keeping inmates meaningfully busy, causing a change in their attitude and behavior, and opening up employment opportunities through vocational skills, further education, and training.

Correctional education in Nigeria is facing a lot of problems. These problems includes poor funding, shortage of infrastructure facilities, instructional resources, shortage of facilitators and poor supervision. The essence of supervision is therefore the monitoring of the performance of school staff, noting the merits and demerits and using befitting and amicable techniques to ameliorate the flaws while still improving on the merits thereby increasing the standard of schools and achieving educational goals. Thus, the concern of educational supervision is the improvement in teaching and teaching environment in order to promote effective teacher performance and learning in the school. It is based on this, that this study seeks to discuss the benefit of correctional education supervision in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Social learning theory was postulated by Bandura (1925-to date). It combines cognitive learning theory (which posits that learning is influenced by psychological factors) and behavioral learning theory (which assumes that learning is based on responses to environmental stimuli). Bandura's model is further enhanced by four requirements for reformative learning: observation (environmental), retention (cognitive), reproduction (cognitive), and motivation (environmental and cognitive). This integrative approach to reformative education is known as the social learning theory. Bandura maintained that inmates' behavior could be reformed through the direct process of instruction as well as observational learning from the prison environment. Prisoners observe the happenings around them, and they also observe what people do. In every society, the learners are surrounded by many influential people (role models). It is of paramount importance to avail inmates' access to different types of models of reformative education for easy learning. Prison officials monitoring the inmates should respond to their change in behavior through reward or punishment (Ismaila, 2020).

Vicarious approval is where the inmate considers what happens to other people when deciding whether or not to copy somebody's behavior. The fundamental tenets of this theory are: 1) reformative education is not purely a behavior; instead, it is more of a cognitive process that can take place in a social context; 2) reformative education can take place by observing an action and following the consequences of that behavior, otherwise known as vicarious reinforcement (prisoners' parole); 3) reinforcement plays a vital role in learning but is not entirely responsible for learning; and 4) a learner is not and should not be a passive recipient of information (Ismaila, 2020).

2.0 Literature Review

Supervision is a Latin Word. Super means 'from the above' and vision means 'to see'. In ordinary sense of the term, supervision means overseeing the activities of others. In management supervision means "Overseeing the subordinates at work with authority and with an aim to guide the employees, if he is doing wrong." (Economis discussion 2020) Supervision is direction, guidance and control of working force with a view to see that they are working according to plan and are keeping time schedule. Further, they are getting all possible help in accomplishing their assigned work. 'Supervision is a joint endeavour in which a practitioner with the help of a supervisor attends to their clients, themselves as part of their client practitioner relationships and the wider systemic context, and by doing so improves the quality of their work, transforms their client relationships, continuously develops themselves, their practice and the wider profession.'

Supervision is the task of achieving the desired results by means of intelligent utilisation of human talents and utilising resources in a manner that provides a challenge to human talent. It is concerned with initiating action, putting into effect the plan and decision by stimulation of the human resources of the enterprise.”(Terry in (Economis discussion 2020). Supervision is the act or function of overseeing something or somebody. It is the process that involves guiding, instructing and correcting someone. A person who performs supervision is a "supervisor", but does not always have the formal title of supervisor (Skolera 2022). School supervision is the process of evaluating, assessing and guiding teachers and staff toward improvement of everyday work. Ultimately, this guidance is based on the end-goal of providing a higher level of learning engagement and improved student outcomes. The people supervising educators and other staff are typically members of administration, including educational leaders (Keiseruniversity 2023).

The objectives of supervision is as follows:

Development of the teaching-learning dynamic:

Supervision of correctional education improves the quality of teaching and learning centres. Skolera (2022) noted that the assessment and improvement of the teaching-learning dynamic are the primary goals of supervision. The goals of supervision are to assist teachers in self-evaluating using the supervisor’s input. Students, teachers, curricular materials and information, classroom management, and the socio-physical environment are the main components of the teaching-learning process.

Improvement of teachers’ skills:

One of the objectives of educational supervision is improving teachers’ skills. The work, ideology, and approach of the teachers form the basis of the planning for supervision. One of the main goals of supervision is to improve teachers’ abilities to work together in order to efficiently complete the majority of the school’s work, which requires them to learn how to collaborate in groups.

Integration of different educational trends:

The current school procedures need to be changed to reflect changes in current educational theory and practice in order to improve the way instructions are delivered and understood. The supervisor has a duty to assist the educational staff in staying up to date with educational trends, researching and learning new pedagogical approaches, and implementing these approaches in the classroom.

Encouragement of collaboration and teamwork:

The process of supervision in education relies on the connection between the teachers and the supervisors. Teachers must learn to work cooperatively in order to complete the majority of schoolwork, and they can only do that if they have a good relationship with the supervisor. The improvement of positive interpersonal relationships is one of the goals of supervision. Healthy relationships between the supervisor and administrator, the instructor and administrator, and the administrators and teachers are necessary for effective and efficient supervision.

3.0 Method

This paper discussed the benefits of supervision correctional education in Nigeria. Data from different secondary sources were employed for the paper. The paper used content analysis to analyze all the literature collected. Only those relevant to the topic were systematically selected. The exploratory method was adopted in the analysis. To ensure the reliability and validity of the study, multiple secondary sources were used to minimize the risk of error. The secondary data were collected directly from textbooks, journals, articles, newspapers and other local and international publications on supervision of correctional education in Nigeria (adapted from Ogunode & Ukozo, 2023 in Ogunode, Ukozor, Ayoko, & Ojochenemi, 2025).

4.0 Data Analysis

4.1 Discussion on Benefits of Correctional Education Supervision

Supervision of correctional education in Nigeria will lead to improvement in facilitators' job performance, attainment of correctional education goals, improvement of inmate academic performance and improvement the quality of teaching-learning

Improvement in facilitators' job performance

Establishing and preserving friendly interpersonal relationships with and among all of the educational staff is one of the fundamental duties of supervision. A friendly connection cannot be established by merely assembling a group of individuals; rather, it must be fostered by living and working with the employees in a way that allows them to exercise strong interpersonal skills. A manager is responsible for treating his/her employees as fellow employees – and not as merely subordinates (Skolera 2022). Educational supervision plays a significant role in a teacher's overall instructional leadership and improvement. When teachers and educators are directly supervised and receive supportive and guided feedback on their work, they can improve their own instructional leadership to support students in achievement of learning objectives. The ultimate goals of supervision are to build better teachers and to improve student learning (Keiseruniversity 2023). Economis discussion (2020) noted that initiating and carrying out the process of supervision in education is done in order to achieve both general and targeted aims and objectives. Educational procedures should always lead to better educational results; so in order to enhance educational outcomes, a school primarily supports supervision and prioritises its importance. The educational programmes' strengths and flaws should be regularly acknowledged by the supervisor, along with any areas that could use development. It should also develop measures to address flaws as they arise. The workers require guidance of supervisor at every step. He clears their doubts and tells them the proper method of doing a job. A sub-ordinate can give better performance when he knows the work he is supposed to do. Ijaduola in Uwe & Godwin, (2019) investigated the relationship that exists between supervisory climate and teacher - student performance in schools. A Significant relationship between frequency of supervisory visits and teacher performance was observed. Akinwumi in Uwe & Godwin, (2019) investigated the impact of motivation and supervision and teacher productivity in Oyo state secondary schools. The result revealed that supervision has a greater impact on teacher productivity. The impact was higher in public schools than in private. Ntukidem in Uwe & Godwin, (2019) studied the performance of teachers under high and low level supervision in Cross River State. The research finding indicated that teachers under high level supervision performed better on their job than their counterparts under low supervision. In a related study, Ntukidem in Uwe & Godwin, (2019) investigated the effects of principals' instructional supervisory effectiveness on teachers' work performance in Cross River State. The research findings indicate that the level of supervision does not significantly influence teachers' work performance.

Attainment of correctional education goals

A supervisor is a representative of the management and a very important figure from workers point of view. He communicates the policies of the management to workers (downward communication) and also provides feed back to the management as to what is happening at the lowest level (upward communication) (Economis discussion 2020). Ensuring that teachers and supervisors collaborate to achieve the goals of the school organisation is the most pivotal component of supervision. It is essential to remember that a school's goals are derived from societal goals and that both teachers and supervisors must collaborate to set the goals for the teaching-learning process (Skolera 2022). A school system can only hope to support students' learning in the proper direction with a highly motivated teacher. Therefore, it is expected that a key result of supervision will be the improvement of teachers' and supervisors' motivation to work together to advance educational objectives (Skolera 2022). Another

function of the process of supervision in education is to assist people in solving problems. For educational instruction to produce the intended results, there must be a continuous process of examination. In situations where supervision makes interventions to assist, it necessitates the ability to problem-solve with regard to the specification of goals and rearranging the conditions for accomplishing goals (Ogunode, & Richard, 2021;Skolera 2022).

Improvement of inmate academic performance

Supervision in education leads to improvement in students' academic performance which includes correctional students (Ntukidem, 2003b;Ogunode, & Ibrahim, 2023;Ogunode, & Fabiyi, 2023). National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN, 2006) listed benefits of supervision to include provision of opportunities for teachers to be groomed through critical study of instructional processes and classroom interactions to carry out their teaching tasks in line with professional codes of conduct. If schools are not supervised adequately, it will have inimical effects on the students' output and the educational objectives may not be achieved, consequently various instructional supervisory techniques should be employed to ensure qualitative and quantities service delivery by the teachers. Ugochukwu, Umeh Nathaniel, & Amobi, (2021);Uko., Umosen,& Caleb, (2015). noted that The main objective of school supervision is to improve school administration, teacher's effectiveness or performance and students' academic performance. In school supervision attention is given more to the teachers because teacher's job performance is crucial to the realization of school objectives.

Improvement the quality of teaching-learning

Effective correctional education supervision enhance quality of teaching and learning in the centres. Ntukidem, (2003b); Ogunode, Olatunde-Aiyedun, & Akin-Ibidiran (2021) and Ogunode & Ajape (2021) observed that instructional supervision aided delivery of quality education in schools. With careful planning and everyone's collaboration, supervision takes proactive measures to improve the teaching-learning environment and the level of instruction should be adjusted to meet the requirements of each student. Regular revisions of the teaching curriculum are necessary as well; it should be life-centred, meaning it should relate to the needs and character of the learners as well as elements of their current family and community lives. The most recent research and educational advancements must be communicated to the teachers to make this successful. It could seem unusual that the process of supervision in education might work for its own improvement, but if we consider that the supervisor sets his/her own goals and employs his/her own strategies; they are able to regularly evaluate whether or not and how well they perform the tasks assigned to them. This entails a self-evaluation of the outcomes or results, adjustments to their approach and processes, as well as advancements in the supervisory staff. Thus, the focus of the school's supervision is on the need for teachers and supervisors to work toward achieving "self-direction, self-evaluation, self-guidance, and self-supervision (Skolera 2022)." Understanding the value of confidence and morale in teaching-learning circumstances and coming up with strategies to boost them is crucial for a supervisor. A goal-achieving mindset is referred to as 'morale.' Morale is seen as a psychological state of mind that arises as a result of how an individual views his current accomplishments and advancement. A demotivated teacher causes considerable harm to his kids because of his continual criticism of authorities, policies, and programmes as well as his avoidance of accountability ((Skolera 2022). Ensuring that the teachers' psychological frameworks are healthy and in line with organisational goals is one of the supervisor's key responsibilities. A supervisor according Economis discussion (2020) to makes systematic arrangement of activities and resources for his group. He assigns work to each worker and delegate's authority to workers. Workers feel frustrated when the work being done by them is not properly arranged. Obioha (2011); Ogundipe, (2008); Ogbaka., Ewelum,& Apiti (2017) advocated for quality supervision to improve quality of education in the prison yards in Nigeria.

4.2 Findings

The paper revealed that supervision of correctional education in Nigeria will lead to improvement in facilitators' job performance, attainment of correctional education goals, improvement in inmate academic performance and improvement in the quality of teaching-learning in the correctional education in Nigeria.

4.3 Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper discussed the benefits of correctional education supervision in Nigeria. The paper concluded that supervision of correctional education in Nigeria will lead to improvement in facilitators' job performance, attainment of correctional education goals, improvement in inmate academic performance and improvement in the quality of teaching-learning in the correctional education in Nigeria.

Based on the findings, the paper recommends that the government through the agencies in charge of instructional supervision to improve the quality of instructional supervision in all the correctional centres. Government should adequately fund these agencies to enable them carry out their supervisory functions.

References

1. Achakzai, J. K., Bukhari, S., & Tahir, M. A. (2015). Women prisoners' access to education and training: A report from Balochistan. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 37(2), 27–42.
2. Adeyeye, B. A. (2019). Challenges and prospects of e-learning for prison education in Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 15(25), 327–335.
3. Akinwumi, P. A. (2000a). The impact of motivation and Supervision and Teacher productivity in Oyo State secondary schools. Unpublished Ph.D Dissertation. University of Ibadan.
4. Akinwumi, P. A. (2000c). *The supervisory techniques and teacher productivity in Oyo State secondary schools*. Unpublished M. Ed thesis. University of Ibadan.
5. Ajelabi, I.D. (2000). *Indiscipline and Policy Implementation problem in Selecting Secondary Schools in Rivers State*. Unpublished M.ED.Thesis, University of Port Harcourt.
6. Aliyu, K., Mustaffa, J., & Nasir, N. M. (2016). An evaluation of prison educational programmes in Kwara State Nigeria. *Association of Sociologists of Education of Nigeria*, 8(1), 103–120.
7. Aziz, T., Iqbal, M. J., & Ahmed, S. Z. (2017). Role of education in prisons for rehabilitation of inmates of prisons. *Paper presented at the MDSRC-2017 Proceedings*, 27-28 December, 2017 Wah/Pakistan.
8. Economis discussion (2020). Management/supervision-meaning <https://www.economicdiscussion.net/management/supervision-meaning/31921>
9. Brazzell, C., Lindahl, M., & Solomon, (2009). "From the Classroom to the Community: Exploring the Role of Education During Incarceration and Re-entry," The Urban Institute, Justice Policy Center, John Jay College of Criminal Justice (2009).
10. Erisman, W., & Contardo, J. B. (2005). "Learning to Reduce Recidivism: A 50-State Analysis of Postsecondary Correctional Education Policy," The Institute for Higher Education Policy (2005).
11. Gerald G. G, (2008), "The Impact of Prison Education Programs on Post-Release Outcomes," Reentry Roundtable on Education (2008).
12. Keiseruniversity (2023).Edu/theories-and-methods-of-school-supervision-and-evaluation <https://www.keiseruniversity.edu/theories-and-methods-of-school-supervision-and->

evaluation/#:~:text=Specifically%2C%20school%20supervision%20or%20educational,engagemen
t%20and%20improved%20student%20outcomes

13. Ismaila, S. (2020). Availability of reformation programmes for prisoner in South West, Nigeria. *UMT, education review*, 3(1),1-24
14. Ijaduola (2008). *The relationship between supervisory climate and teacher - student performance in schools*, Unpublished M. Ed. thesis. University of Ibadan.
15. Ntukidem, P. J. (2003a). Supervision and teachers' job effectiveness in Cross Rivers State Secondary Schools. *International Journal of Educational Administration, Planning and Research*, 1(2), 42-47.
16. Ntukidem, P. J. (2003b). Principals, instructional supervisory effectiveness and teachers, work performance in secondary schools in cross rivers state. *International Journal of Educational Administration, Planning and Research*, 1(2), 132-143.
17. Ogunode, N. J. & Ukozo, C. U (2023). Exploring alternative funding options for universities education in a depressed economy. *Fan, Ta'lim, Madaniyat Va Innovatsiya*, 2(10), 64-76. <https://mudarrisziyo.uz/index.php/innovatsiya/article/view/451>
18. Ogunode, N., J., Ukuzor, C., U., Ayoko, V., O., & Ojochenemi, U., B (2025). Adequate Funding Panacea for Development of Correctional Education in Nigeria. *"IQTISODIYOT VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYA"*, 2(4), 15-23
19. Ogunode N., J., Edinoh, K & Odo, R., C (2023). Development of Tertiary Education in Prison and Correctional Centres in Nigeria. *Best journal of innovation in science, research and development* 2(6)302-310
20. Ogunode, N., J. (2025). Benefit of Digital Literacy for Academic staff and Students of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. *American Journal of Alternative Education* 2(2),43-53
21. Ogunode, N., J. & Ibrahim, A. (2023). Instructional Supervision in Nigerian Schools: Problems and Solutions. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 6(4),156-165
22. Ogunode, N., J. & Fabiyi, O., T. (2023) Supervision of Economics Programme in Post-Basic Education and Career Development (PBECD) in Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 6(3),199-205
23. Ogunode, N. J. Olatunde-Aiyedun, T. G. & Akin-Ibidiran T. Yemi (2021) Challenges Preventing Effective Supervision of Universal Basic Education in Kuje Area Council of Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, (16), 63-72.
24. Ogunode N. J. & Ajape T. S. (2021) Supervision of Secondary School Education in Nigeria: Problems and Suggestions. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements (EJHEA)* 2(6), 71-76 25.
25. Ogunode, N. J. & Richard, U. N (2021) Supervision of Secondary School Education in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja: Problems and the Way Forward. *International Journal on Orange Technology* 3(8),47-56
26. Obioha, E. E. (2011). Challenges and reforms in the Nigeria prisons system. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 27(2): 95–109.
27. Ogunoipe, O. A. (2008). Education behind bars: The Nigerian experience. *The Reformer*, 3(3), 32–38.
28. Ogbaka, L.C., Ewelum, J.N., & Apiti, A. (2017). Utilization of educational programmes in reformation of prison inmates in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Education and Training*, 3(2), 86-91.

29. Ore, C. I. (2006). Non-formal education needs of adult inmates of Nsukka divisional prisons and The Millennium Development Goals. *Journal of Adult Education in Nigeria*, (NNCAE), 11, 66–75.
30. Pew Center on the States, (2011). “State of Recidivism: The Revolving Door of America’s Prisons,” The Pew Charitable Trusts (April 2011) p. 1.
31. Pew Center on the States, (2010). “Prison Count 2010: State Population Declines for the First Time in 38 Years,” The Pew Charitable Trusts (April 2010) p. 5.
32. Rhode, L., 2004. What’s wrong with prisoners’ hearts and minds networks. Retrieved from <http://www.employeradvisorsnetwork.com/documents/21stcenturyfirm.pde>.
33. Sarkinfada, H. & Garba, A., D (2023). Prison Education or Correctional Education in Nigeria. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* (17) ,21-27
34. Skolera (2022). The Huge Importance Of The Process Of Supervision In Education <https://blog.skolera.com/importance-of-supervision-education/>
<https://blog.skolera.com/importance-of-supervision-education/>
35. The Effect of Prison Education Programs on Recidivism, (2010).” The Journal of Correctional Education (Dec 2010) pp. 316-334.
36. Uko, E. S., Umosen, A. O., & Caleb, E. F. (2015). Administrators’ resource management practices and teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Eket education zone of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 3(2), 13-20.
37. Ugochukwu, A., V. Umeh Nathaniel, U & Amobi, A B. (2021). Influence of Supervision of Instruction on Teachers’ Productivity in Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research* (3),27-31
38. Wolford, B.I., 1989. Correctional facilities. In S.B. Merriam & P.M. Cunningham (Eds), Handbook of adult and continuing education. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.
39. Zoukis, C. (2011). What is Prison Education and Why Should We Care?
<https://federalcriminaldefenseattorney.com/what-is-prison-education-and-why-should-we-care-html/>